

NASA Sun-Earth Connection Program Strategic Mission & Technology Requirements (2006-2015)¹

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Abstract—Our variable star, the Sun, is the source of varying solar wind, electromagnetic radiation and electromagnetic particles that interact with the Planets and the Galaxy. The Sun-Earth Connection (SEC) Theme in the NASA Office of Space Science (OSS) has a strategic goal to understand our changing Sun and its effects on the Solar System, Life and Society. The SEC Roadmap defines the major science questions or Quests from which a series of strategic roadmap missions are identified to provide the measurements to address these quests. The SEC Roadmap strategy is to develop a series of modest, synergistic missions integrated with a few more capable break-through missions. Together, these missions will allow us to discover and understand the connected Sun-Earth system in the spatial, temporal, and spectral domain from widely distributed vantage points in space. These strategic missions are being pursued in three general flight program areas including Solar Terrestrial Probes, A Space Weather Research Network in the new Living With a Star Program, and through Frontier Probes. These missions build on the International Solar Terrestrial Physics Program (ISTP) and SEC missions in the 1990's and early 2000's where the importance of system understanding of the variable Sun and interaction with the Earth's geospace was identified.

This paper describes the planned SEC strategic missions planned for the period 2006-2015 and their technology requirements. These missions range from individual spacecraft to clusters and constellations of micro-nano satellite missions utilizing both imaging and in-situ instrumentation. Enabling technologies include micro-nano satellite and instrumentation along with solar sail propulsion providing reduced flight times and unique non-keplerian orbits to extend traditional vantage points. Enhancing technology requirements related to instruments and subsystems are described that will improve payload mass-fraction, improved performance and lower cost.

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3. SUMMARY

1. SEC STRATEGIC PERSPECTIVE

The strategic plans for the SEC Program are contained in the "Sun Earth Connection Roadmap, Strategic Planning for 2000-2025" [1] [2]. The SEC roadmap, and roadmaps from the Exploration of the Solar System (ESS), Astronomical Search for Origins (ASO), and Structure and Evolution of the Universe (SEU) themes, form the basis for the OSS 2000 Strategic Plan which is being incorporated into the NASA 2000 Strategic Plan.

The SEC Program domain of study addressed in the SEC Roadmap includes solar processes, as well as the interaction of solar plasma and radiation with the Earth, other planets, and the Galaxy. Solar, heliospheric and geospace research to date has provided some basic understanding of these processes. Recent investigations carried out by the SEC missions of the 1990's and early 2000's, as shown in

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Figure 1 “The ISTP [3]/SEC Constellation of Missions,” have utilized improved in-situ and imaging capability and have demonstrated the importance of the interconnected systems perspective. Our challenge now is to discover; understand/model quantitatively the full system of complex interactions that characterize the relationship of the Sun with the Solar System. This effort will require critical measurements from new vantage points in the Solar System and the local interstellar medium. The new scientific knowledge acquired in this program will be of direct benefits to our increasingly space-dependent society by quantitatively determining the effects of solar variability on human technology, humans in space and terrestrial climate.

Figure 1 - The ISTP/SEC Constellation of Missions

The SEC program goals are expressed through four fundamental Quests or questions that are inherently interconnected. These SEC Quests are shown as questions in Figure 2, which depicts the effects of the variable star, our Sun, on the planets, and in particular, the Earth.

Figure 2 - The Sun-Earth Connected System

Science campaigns have been identified in the SEC Roadmap for which series of strategic missions have been identified to gather the necessary measurements. These campaigns form a plan of prioritized missions according to their scientific contribution to the Quest, synergy with other SEC missions, and technology readiness. The coordinated set of strategic missions identified in these campaigns

provide the motivation for timely technology development in support of mission development including coordinated use of multiple spacecraft, techniques for travel to currently inaccessible regions of space, and lowering spacecraft and instrument costs. The overall SEC strategic flowdown for these technology requirements is shown in Figure 3. This flowdown was described in more detail in a previous paper [18] for the period (2000-2025).

Figure 3 - Sun-Earth Connection Roadmap: Strategic Flowdown

As discussed in the SEC Roadmap [2], the scientific and technical trends motivating these quests and campaigns include:

- The study of global systems through overlapping missions and multipoint measurements provided by microsat, and eventually nanosat, constellations
- 3D imaging through the use of unique vantage points with advanced propulsion and high-rate deep space communication
- The focus on the internal structure of the solar atmosphere with advanced instrumentation
- Expanding our measurements from geospace to the planets in collaboration with the ESS Program
- Exploring the boundaries of the solar system with Frontier Probe missions using advanced propulsion techniques
- Developing the science understanding necessary to effectively address those aspects of the connected Sun-Earth system that directly affect life and society

The resulting strategic missions that are being pursued in the 2006-2015 period encompass three general flight program areas; the Solar Terrestrial Probes, the Space Weather Research Network in the new Living with a Star Program, and Frontier Probes which are still in the planning stages. The SEC STP and LWS Strategic Mission Schedule in the context of the solar cycle is shown in Figure 4. Both the STP and LWS/SWRN programs are contained in the NASA OSS budget and the synergistic

missions in these programs are identified through the OSS strategic planning process.

2. SEC STRATEGIC MISSION & TECHNOLOGY REQUIREMENTS (2006-2015)

2.1 Solar Terrestrial Probes

The Solar Terrestrial Probes Program (STP) [4] is comprised of a coordinated sequence of strategic solar and geospace missions that are identified in the SEC Roadmap and address fundamental science questions in the first and second Quests: "Why does the Sun vary?", and "How do the planets respond to solar variations?". STP missions stimulate the use of advanced technology and utilize in-situ and remote sensing techniques, from both individual and multiple platforms to understand solar variability cause and effects over vast spatial scales. The STP missions planned for the Period from 2006-2015 presently include Magnetospheric Multiscale (MMS), Geospace

Electrodynamic Connections (GEC) and Magnetospheric Constellation (MC). MMS, GEC and MC were originally described as Geospace Multiprobes in 1997 [5]. These missions are planned as follow-on to the first three missions of the STP series: the Thermosphere, Ionosphere and Mesosphere, Energetics and Dynamics (TIMED) (2001), Solar Terrestrial Relations Observatory (STEREO) (2004) and Solar-B (2005).

2.1.1 Magnetospheric Multiscale (MMS) [6]—MMS is a multiple spacecraft STP mission designed to study magnetic reconnection, charged particle acceleration, and turbulence in key boundary regions of the Earth's magnetosphere. MMS will focus on plasma micro-processes and their linkage to meso and global scale processes. MMS will operate in different regions of the magnetosphere than Cluster II which will study only magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) scale phenomena.

Figure 4 - Sun-Earth Connection STP & LWS Strategic Mission Schedule

Broad regions of the magnetosphere are connected by fundamental processes operating in thin boundary layers. MMS will employ multi-point measurements that uniquely separate temporal and three dimensional spatial variations to address these small scale plasma processes.

The MMS science measurements include magnetic and electric fields, electron and ion plasma spectrometers, energetic particles, and plasma waves all with high temporal and spatial resolution, and burst event recording.

MMS is planned to be implemented through at least four identical spacecraft in four orbit phases with orbit adjust capability and variable spacecraft separation. Multiscale measurements, extending from microprocesses to and including MHD scales, are common to all phases which include:

- Dayside Magnetopause/Near-Earth Magnetotail Investigation at 1.2 Re x 12 Re x 10 degrees inclination
- Near-Earth Neutral Line/Magnetopause Flanks Investigation at an apogee of 20-30 Re
- Distant Magnetotail Studies at an apogee of 100-120 Re using two sets of double lunar swingby maneuvers
- Magnetopause Skimming/Mid-Tail Investigation Phase in a 10 Re x 40 Re polar orbit

Technology enhancements to be pursued in support of the MMS development include:

- High I_{SP} chemical propulsion (biprop > 325 I_{SP} ΔV 1100 M/S)
- Instrument miniaturization including boom lightweighting for plasma and E-field measurements
- Data systems (on-board processing, storage, and compression)
- Spacecraft attitude determination at 10-20 RPM
- Constellation control for relative spacecraft position determination to 1% separation
- Autonomous operations of satellite constellations enabled by advanced on-board computation capabilities
- Passive control of spacecraft potential in solar arrays and thermal control surfaces and active potential control, e.g., plasma charge balancing system
- Low cost manufacturing for electrically conductive solar arrays

2.1.2 Geospace Electrodynamic Connections (GEC) [7]—GEC will determine the role of the Ionosphere/Thermosphere (I-T) in the electro-dynamic environment of near-Earth space. The GEC mission is being designed to determine the spatial and temporal dimensions of the ion-neutral interactions by means of which the I-T system processes energy imparted to it from the magnetosphere. Through multi-spacecraft sampling of the I-T region over a broad range of magnetic latitudes and local times and focused dipping campaigns in the most important coupling zones, GEC will answer two fundamental questions about the coupled I-T system and about the coupling of this system to the magnetosphere:

- How does the I-T system respond to magnetospheric forcing?
- How is the I-T system dynamically coupled to the magnetosphere?

GEC science measurements includes neutral particles, charged particles, and electric and magnetic fields utilizing

in-situ sensing techniques complemented by ground-based remote observations.

Several identical spacecraft will utilize formation flying and orbit reconfiguration, with sufficient fuel to conduct a dozen week long “dipping” campaigns to the vicinity of 130 km altitude.

Technology enhancements to be pursued in support of the GEC development include:

- Aerodynamic stability for dipping spacecraft
- Atomic oxygen resistant material
- High I_{SP} chemical propulsion >325
- Secondary energy storage
- Neutral flow sensor
- Lightweight electric field instrument booms
- Low cost manufacturing of electrically conductive solar arrays
- Constellation management during dipping campaigns

2.1.3 Magnetospheric Constellation (MC) [8]—The Dynamics, Reconnection, Response And Configuration Coupling Observatory (DRACO) has been identified as a Magnetotail Constellation STP mission which will address the primary science question: How does the magnetotail store, transport, and release matter and energy? The mission science objectives include:

- Understand the responses of the magnetotail to the solar wind
- Map the linkages between the local and global processes
- Determine the equilibria of the magnetotail
- Reveal the instabilities of the magnetotail

Instrumentation includes magnetic fields, plasmas and energetic particle measurements.

The mission consists of a constellation of 50-100 fully functional 10 kg-sized nano-satellites that acquire vector images of the magnetic and plasma flow fields and form a network of space weather observatories. Elliptical orbits are planned with dense sampling from 7-40 Re with a spatial resolution of 1-2 Re.

Enabling technologies to be pursued in support of the MC development include:

- Miniaturized instrumentation
 - magnetic fields,
 - plasmas and
 - energetic particles
- Integrated nanosat sciencecraft systems development
 - Advanced multifunctional structures
 - Lightweight, high output battery cells
 - Ultra-low power C&DH subsystem
 - X-Band transponder
 - High performance, low power mini-thrusters
 - Attitude control systems for nanosats

- Constellation operations management and autonomy
 - Autonomy for onboard and ground operation using heuristic systems
- Advanced software for constellation data processing
 - Advanced data synthesis and visualization techniques
 - Advanced techniques for data assimilation into numerical global simulation models

The NASA New Millennium Program Space Technology-5 Mission [19] is planned for launch in 2003 with three nanosat-sized satellites. ST-5 will flight validate several of these technologies and provide a transition from the use of clusters of small satellites to constellations of nanosats for MC-type missions.

2.2 Living With A Star (LWS) Space Weather Research Network (SWRN)

A Space Weather Research Network (SWRN) of solar and geospace missions, conducted as part of the NASA Living with a Star (LWS) Program [9] [17] will provide the scientific measurements from key spatial vantages, to achieve or accomplish the fourth Quest in the SEC Roadmap and determine how solar variability directly affects life and society.

The importance of space weather is evidenced in the effects that solar variability can have on advanced technology, humans in space, and terrestrial climate. The sphere of the human environment continues to expand above and beyond our planet and we look to an increasing dependence on space-based systems and a permanent presence of humans in low Earth orbit and outward into the solar system. Specifically, improved space weather information is needed to mitigate such effects as; human radiation exposure in space and during high altitude atmospheric flight; the radiation tolerance of technologies used in terrestrial and space communications and navigation systems as well as solar-drivers of near- and long-term climate change for the Earth.

The goal of the LWS Program is to provide the scientific foundation necessary for the development of a national policy and the implementation of inter-agency responses to space weather. The LWS Program is responsive and congruent with the National Space Weather Program, managed by the Office of the Federal Coordinator of Meteorology [10], and the Space Weather Architecture Study, initiated by the Department of Defense [11]. An initial aim of LWS is the clear specification of the behavior of the coupled Earth-Sun system. With this system's specification, an attempt will be made to identify the critical physical processes that dominate the system; an activity which leads to the development of an accurate predictive capability.

The LWS Program elements include the Space Weather Research Network, Theory, Modeling and Data Analysis

(TMDA), and Space Environment Testbeds (SET). These elements are described in the LWS Pre-Formulation Study [12].

The SWRN is planned to be implemented during the next solar maximum 2010-2011. The primary LWS/ SWRN missions described include the Solar Dynamics Observatory (SDO), the Solar Sentinels, including Inner Heliospheric Constellation and Farside, Radiation Belt Mappers (RBM) and Ionospheric Mappers (IM) and are shown in Figure 5. Additionally, a Solar Probe mission is described as complementary to the SWRN, and Solar Polar Imager mission is described as a next generation SWRN. As shown in Figure 4, the Solar Net Missions observe the Sun at regions between one solar radii and one AU and track the origination and propagation of disturbances, while the geospace Net measures the downstream effects in key regions around the Earth.

The planning for the primary missions assumes that technology readiness levels (TRL) of five or above will be employed to ensure mission readiness in support of measurements in the next solar cycle. A TRL of five indicates that the technology has component and/or breadboard validation in the relevant environment. The missions will exploit technologies which can improve performance, improve the payload mass fraction, and/or reduce costs etc. and these will be identified as the SWRM formulation progresses. Some of the key technologies of the primary SWRM missions include:

- High-efficiency, triple-junction, GaAs solar cells
- Radiation resistant, fast read-out, 4096x4096 CCD arrays
- Li-ion battery
- Ka-band antenna system
- Low power, lightweight GPS transceiver
- Large, radiation resistant solid state memory

Presently, an LWS program-level Science Architecture Team (SAT) is examining the LWS Program requirements and architecture from an overall system point of view. The SAT will make recommendations regarding the SWRM architecture and the relationship to on-going and planned SEC programs in order to identify and guide the formulation of the SWRM system of missions commensurate with the available budget.

The TMDA element will provide improved understanding of space weather and solar variability and its effect on long term climate change. It will also enable and develop improved specification models and predictive capability in addressing the vast region from the solar atmosphere to the Earth's ionosphere. A supporting effort underway at this time is the Community Coordinated Modelling Center [13], an interagency space weather modelling activity aimed at generating the next generation of space weather models.

LWS Missions For The Next Solar Maximum

Figure 5 - LWS Missions for the Next Solar Maximum

The SET element aims to improve the engineering approach to accommodate and/or mitigate the effects of solar variability on spacecraft design and operations. The SET element plans to employ LWS flight opportunities, in addition to commercial, DOD and CNES-provided Ariane-launched opportunities to better understand the space environment effects on current and emerging technologies and biosystems. These results will improve risk management and ground test protocols for new technologies, and the environmental guidance available for spacecraft design and operations.

The flight and ground segments of the SWRN will be complemented by on-going and planned space and ground assets and supplemented with scientific modeling and analysis capability. The deployment and use of these assets will improve the scientific understanding and enable a more effective space weather capability through which operational agencies can monitor and predict space weather. The resulting benefits will impact a wide array of users who can apply this information to the design and protection of our terrestrial and space-based systems of the future. A description of the SWRM missions identified in the LWS Pre-Formulation Study is contained below.

2.2.1 Solar Dynamics Observatory—The SDO will observe the Sun's dynamics and help to understand the nature and source of variations from the stellar core to the turbulent

solar atmosphere. As part of the LWS program, SDO will focus on the solar phenomena which have an impact on Earth and near-Earth geospace. The SDO mission is planned as a 3-axis stabilized spacecraft in a high-inclination geosynchronous orbit. This orbit will permit the use of one primary ground station and the accommodation of high data rates from the imaging instruments. The current mission concept includes a helioseismograph to study the solar interior, a magnetograph and coronal imagers to study the Sun's atmosphere, and measurements of solar luminosity and irradiance in the UV and EUV.

2.2.2 Sentinels—The notional Sentinels will provide a global view of the heliosphere and describe the transition and evolution of eruptions and flares from the Sun to Earth. The Sentinels aim to discover, understand, and model the connection between solar phenomena and magnetospheric/ionospheric disturbances. The notional Sentinel mission is planned to have two distinct elements: Four Inner Heliospheric Sentinels (IHS) and a Far Side Sentinel (FSS).

2.2.2.1 Inner Heliospheric Sentinel—The notional IHS consists of four spinning satellites in heliocentric orbits covering radial distances of between 0.5 and 0.95 AU's. The IHS will carry in-situ instrumentation to determine the ambient structure of the inner heliosphere and follow the evolution of large scale features. These measurements

include solar wind plasma and composition, vector magnetic field, energetic particles. The IHS observations will provide absolute calibration of remote sensing measurements made from SDO and FSS.

2.2.2.2 Far Side Sentinel—A notional Far Side Sentinel (FSS) is planned to address the 3D structure of the Sun interior and the life-cycle of magnetic active regions. The FSS orbit utilizes a Venus gravity assist to attain a 1 AU orbit nearly out of phase with the Earth on the far side of the Sun slowly drifting from 180 to 120 degrees separation from the Earth.

The 3-axis stabilized FSS plans to utilize in-situ instrumentation (magnetometer, solar wind analyzer, and energetic particle detector) to provide a key vantage point for the determination of inner heliospheric structures in cooperation with the other Sentinels. FSS remote sensing instrumentation will provide continuous and whole surface imaging of the photosphere and the solar corona, hence allowing the evolution of solar active regions. An on-board Doppler-Magnetograph will enable solar seismology to be carried out in conjunction with SDO to determine the inner structure of the Sun.

2.2.3 Radiation Belt Mapper—The notional RBM will help to understand the origin and dynamics of the radiation belts and determine the evolution of penetrating radiation during magnetic storms.

A notional RBM mission employs an array of up to six spin-stabilized small satellites in low-inclination orbits @ 6.5 Re x 500 KM altitude supplemented by one spin-stabilized satellite in a 2.5 Re x 500 KM orbit to provide a large-scale, time-dependent characterization of particles and fields in the Earth’s inner magnetosphere. In-situ instrumentation is planned for these spinning spacecraft to include energetic ions, protons, electrons, magnetic fields, electric fields, and ULF/VLF waves.

2.2.4 Ionospheric Mapper—The notional IM will gather knowledge of how the ionosphere behaves as a system, linking solar energy with the Earth’s atmosphere. Space weather phenomena of particular importance that will be investigated by IM include enhanced atmospheric drag on low orbiting spacecraft, the origins of ionospheric scintillations and the large ionospheric currents driven by substorms which cause destructive induction currents in ground-based power grids.

The notional IM mission is envisioned as two identical 3-axis stabilized satellites in low inclination 450 km circular orbits and six identical 3-axis stabilized spacecraft in six orbit planes 30 degrees apart at 450 km circular polar. All satellites are planned to incorporate chiefly in-situ instrumentation with some additional remote sensing experiments to obtain, for example, plasma density profiles. New techniques that take advantage of the global coverage of the Ionospheric Mappers, such as GPS tomographic observations, are also being considered for this unprecedented array of measurement platforms.

2.2.5 Solar Probe—Solar Probe [14] [15] a complementary LWS mission, plans to obtain “ground truth” of the solar wind in the solar corona @ 3 solar radii altitude and address the following fundamental science questions such as:

- What heats the solar corona and accelerates the solar wind?
- What are the sources of the solar wind in the corona?
- What roles do turbulence and waves play in the coronal heating process?
- What are the characteristics of the structures in the polar regions of the sun?

As described in the Solar Probe STDT Report [15], the Solar Probe is planned to be launched toward Jupiter and arrive at perihelion as shown in Figure 6. Solar Probe will pass over the north polar region of the Sun, cross the equatorial region, then pass the south polar region as it moves away from the Sun with scientific measurements taken 24 hours before and 24 hours after the equatorial crossing. A retrograde flyby maneuver at Jupiter will rotate the plane of the orbit, providing an ecliptic inclination of 90 degrees, and will reduce the perihelion radius to 4 solar radii or about 2.8 million kilometers. This maneuver is also important in establishing the "quadrature" geometry at perihelion. Quadrature is defined here when the sun-spacecraft-Earth angle is 90 degrees (at perihelion). This allows the unique spacecraft configuration employing a combined shield/antenna. The solar powered spacecraft is dominated by the thermal shield that will protect the components from the intense heat at perihelion. The shield has its unique shape because it will satisfy two functions - as a shield and as a large antenna for communications to the Earth.

Figure 6 - Near-Perihelion Activities

As shown in Figure 6, the heat shield is always pointing toward the Sun to keep the instrumentation in the shield's umbra at a nominal temperature of 20°C.

The strawman instrument payload includes an all-sky coronagraph, a visible magnetograph, an ultra-violet spectrometer, plasma spectrometers, energetic particle instrument, plasma wave sensor, and magnetometers.

The enabling technologies for the Solar Probe include high temperature solar arrays and thermal shield/antenna capable of operating at temperatures of <2400 degrees kelvin. A major breakthrough in the shield design occurred during a materials testing program which began in 1996. The materials were tested to measure their optical properties which would determine the shield operating temperature at perihelion. In addition, they were tested to measure their mass loss or sublimation properties at high temperatures which would determine the cleanliness of the spacecraft when measuring the natural plasma environment near perihelion. The results of the tests of the optical properties show that the absorptivity/emissivity ratio is about 20% less than predicted and that the shield will operate significantly cooler than anticipated. Also, the mass loss test results indicate that the sublimation rates at perihelion will be more than 10 times lower than anticipated. Because of these results, it is predicted that the spacecraft will not affect the natural plasma environments to be measured near the sun.

2.2.6 Solar Polar Imager (SPI)—SPI is a notional mission, enabled by Solar Sails, to be considered in the next generation of LWS missions. Solar Polar Imager [2] address the fundamental question: How do the polar regions of the Sun affect the dynamics of the global corona and reveal the secrets of the solar cycle.

The SPI spacecraft would be a three-axis and spin stabilized solar powered platform in a circular 0.5 AU solar polar orbit in a 3:1 resonance with the Earth. 30 degree to 150 degree separation from Earth would complement the LWS/SWRM.

As shown in Figure 7, the first observations of the Sun from above the poles will provide valuable information concerning the solar cycle, solar activity, the 3-D structure of the dynamic solar corona and solar wind, and even space weather.

Figure 7 - Solar Polar Imager

The investigations are planned to include a coronagraph, an all-sky imager to follow the CME's from the Sun to 1 AU

and beyond, a dopplergraph/magnetograph for helioseismology and measurements of the magnetic field, an EUV or X-ray camera and an irradiance monitor. A lightweight fields and particles package would contain a plasma spectrometer, magnetometer, and energetic particle detector and would relate properties of the solar wind to solar and coronal features and extend measurements of heliospheric latitude variations made by Ulysses inward to 0.5 AU.

The technology requirements for the SPI includes a solar sail propulsion, lightweight subsystems and instruments, high-rate telemetry from deep space, and AI event selection and spacecraft autonomy.

2.3 Frontier Probes

Frontier Probes are larger, more capable missions needed to achieve break-through science. The Frontier Probes described in the SEC Roadmap include the Interstellar Probe, driven by the third Quest, How do the Sun and galaxy interact?.

2.3.1 Interstellar Probe (IP) [16]—The Interstellar Probe is aimed at improving our understanding of the nature of the interstellar medium and its interaction with the solar system.

As shown in Figure 8, the Interstellar Probe would pass through the boundaries of the heliosphere and begin exploring nearby interstellar space.

Figure 8 - Interstellar Probe

In-situ measurements would be made of the properties and composition of interstellar plasma, neutrals, dust, and low energy cosmic rays. In-situ measurements and global imaging would also be used to determine the heliospheric structure and dynamics. Finally the IR emission of the

zodiacal dust cloud would be mapped and the distribution of interplanetary dust and small kuiper belt objects would be measured.

The mission involves sending a spacecraft to 200+ AU in 15 years with solar sail propulsion. The sail would be used to decelerate, swing by the Sun at 0.25 AU, and then accelerate the spacecraft towards the nose of the heliosphere. The sail would be jettisoned at ~5 AU and the spacecraft would coast to 200+ AU, exploring the Kuiper Belt, heliospheric boundaries, and interstellar medium.

The enabling technology for the ISP includes solar sail propulsion, low-mass/power optimized instrumentation, advanced Ka band telecommunications, lightweight low-cost spacecraft, and integral design of structure and electronics.

3. SUMMARY

The challenges posed by the missions and technology development required to implement the SEC strategic missions in the period 2006-2015 are central to the SEC program. These missions and technologies are the enabling elements that provide the great promise to expand our vision, increase our scientific understanding of the changing sun, and its effects on the solar system, life and society, and to apply this knowledge for the benefit of mankind in the 21st Century and beyond.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author wishes to acknowledge the efforts of the SEC Team who supported the preparation of the SEC Roadmap, the LWS Pre-Formulation Study Report, the STDT Reports and mission studies for the Solar Terrestrial Probes, the Solar Probe, the Frontier Probes and the derivation of the resulting SEC mission technology requirements.

REFERENCES

- [1] Sun-earth Connection Web Site:
<http://sec.gsfc.nasa.gov>
- [2] The Sun-Earth Connection Roadmap, Strategic Planning for 2000-2025, Sun-Earth Connection Roadmap Team, Keith T. Strong, Lockheed-Martin Advanced Technology Center, Chair and James A. Slavin, Goddard Space Flight Center, Co-Chair, 1999
- [3] ISTP Web Site: <http://www-istp.gsfc.nasa.gov/>
- [4] STP Web Site: http://sec.gsfc.nasa.gov/stp_home.htm
- [5] Geospace Multiprobes STDT Report, December 1997
- [6] MMS STDT Report, NASA TM-2000-209883, December 1999
MMS Web Site: <http://sec.gsfc.nasa.gov/magmulti.htm>

- [7] GEC STDT Report
GEC Web Site: <http://sec.gsfc.nasa.gov/gec.htm>

- [8] MC STDT Report
MC Web Site: <http://sec.gsfc.nasa.gov/magcon.htm>

- [9] Living With a Star Web Site:
<http://sec.gsfc.nasa.gov/lws.htm>

- [10] National Space Weather Program, Implementation Plan, National Space Weather Program Council, 1997

- [11] Space Weather Architecture Study, National Security Space Architect, 1999

- [12] LWS Pre-Formulation Study, Program Architecture, August 2000

- [13] CCMC Web Site: <http://ccmc.gsfc.nasa.gov>

- [14] Solar Probe STDT Report
Solar Probe Web Site:
http://umbra.nascom.nasa.gov/solar_connections/probe.html

- [15] Solar Probe Mission (J. Randolph/JPL, Proceedings of 2001 IEEE Aerospace Conference, Big Sky, Montana, March 2001)

- [16] Wallace, R. A., "Precursor Missions to Interstellar Exploration," Proceedings of the 1999 IEEE Aerospace Conference, Aspen, CO, Track 2/Paper 114, March 10, 1999, p. 5.

- [17] "Living With A Star," The NASA Space Weather Initiative, IAF October 2000, A. V. Diaz/GSFC

- [18] NASA Sun-Earth Connection Program Planning and Technology Requirements (2000-2025), M. A. Calabrese, et al, Proceedings of 2000 IEEE Aerospace Conference, Big Sky, Montana, March 2000

- [19] New Millennium Program ST-5 mission Web Site:
<http://nmp.jpl.nasa.gov/st5/index.html>

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